

Deir el-Bala'izah, Monastery of Abba Apollo

also known as "Dayr al-Balayza", "Deir el-Balaiza"

Secondary source

Entered by Alexandra Konstantinidou

* Secondary Source entry, prepared from a literature review by a Ph.D. RA

Entry tags: Monastic Order, Egyptian Christianity, Early Christianity, Middle Egypt, Religious Group, Egypt, Monastery, Christian Traditions, Religious Place

The Monastery of Abba Apollo in Deir el-Bala'izah is situated on the left bank of the Nile, circa 18km to the south of Asiut, in Egypt. The first to investigate the site was F. Petrie (1907; 1909) who carried out brief excavation research, mainly in quest for papyri. Much later, P. Grossman conducted fieldwork and provided a more detailed description of the settlement (see: Grossmann 1993). It is considered that the first monastic habitations were adjusted in a pre-existing (presumably Roman?) quarry that was cut into the cliff that carries the desert plateau. Then the settlement extended down the rather steep slope and it was protected by an enclosure wall. The base of the wall is thicker as it was made of large stones connected with mud; the wall itself is constructed of mud-brick. It had a main gate on the east and several side entrances on the sides. The ruins in front of the main gate are interpreted as a guest-house. The entire settlement occupies an almost trapezoid area, where the remains of buildings still stand - some of them at a considerable height. The buildings were constructed of mud-brick and there is evidence that many of them had multiple storeys. They are gathered especially on the upper slope and inside a row of the quarry caves. Two large three-aisled structures are interpreted as refectories. The elongated buildings around them were identified by Grossmann (1993, 190-194) as dormitories. However, Wipszycka (2009, 119-120) argued that they could have been either store rooms either buildings of industrial function. Another building, which is characterised by a number of niches, was considered to be the library of the monastery, yet such an interpretation should be dealt with caution. Remains of two churches were discovered: a small church was built at the south-eastern corner of the site and another one to the west, around and outside a quarry cave. The water was supplied by a rectangular well.

Date Range: 650 CE - 800 CE

Region: Al Balayzah

Region tags: Egypt, Deir el-Bala'izah

Deir el-Bala'izah - Monastery of Abba Apollo near Balayzah

Status of Participants:

✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Other [specify]: Rocky hill used as a rock-cut quarry.

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– No

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: No single feature, but features as parts of structures.

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Notes: It is considered that "some ancient quarries were first fitted out as dwellings; then down the slope, a whole series of buildings was constructed" (Coquin et al. 1991, 786). According to this view, the settlement was developed progressively.

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Collapsed

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

– Other [specify]: No

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

– Natural phenomena

Notes: Abandoned and deteriorated due to natural decay.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Field doesn't know

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Abba Apollo (Christian Saint).

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Grossmann, P. Die Unterkunftsbauten des Koinobitenklosters 'Dair al-Balayza' im Vergleich mit den Eremitagen der Mönche von Kellia. In P. Bridel (ed.), *Le site monastique copte des Kellia: Sources historiques et explorations archéologiques*, 33-39. Geneva 1986.

– Source 2: Grossmann, P. Neue frühchristliche Funde aus Ägypten." In N. Duval (ed.), *Actes du XIe congrès international d'archéologie chrétienne* (Lyon, Vienne, Grenoble, Genève, Aoste, 21-28 septembre 1986),

1879-1882. Rome 1989.

– Source 3: Coquin, R.-G., M. S. Martin and P. Grossmann. Dayr al-Bala'yzah. In A. S. Atiya (ed.), *The Coptic Encyclopedia*, vol. 3, 786-787. New York 1991.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

– Other [specify]: Quarry

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.trismegistos.org/place/3025>

– Source 2 URL: <http://imperium.ahlfeldt.se/places/37293.html>

– Source 3 URL: <https://pleiades.stoa.org/places/756520>

Notes: Source 4: <https://4care-skos.mf.no/4care-sites/31/>

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Notes: F. Petrie carried out a very brief, non systematic excavation in the site in the early 20th century.

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1907

Name of excavation

–Official or descriptive name: Deir el-Bala'izah

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Notes: It is situated in the desert, yet not too far from the Nile valley.

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Field doesn't know

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Field doesn't know

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Field doesn't know

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: A significant corpus of Coptic and Greek manuscripts was found in Deir el-Bala'izah (Kahle, P. E. Bala'izah. Coptic Texts from Deir el-Bala'izah in Upper Egypt. London 1954).

Sources and Excavations

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- Source 1: Grossmann, P. Die Unterkunftsbauten des Koinobitenklosters 'Dair al-Balayza' im Vergleich mit den Eremitagen der Mönche von Kellia. In P. Bridel (ed.), *Le site monastique copte des Kellia: Sources historiques et explorations archéologiques*, 33-39. Geneva 1986.
- Source 2: Grossmann, P. Neue frühchristliche Funde aus Ägypten." In N. Duval (ed.), *Actes du XIe congrès international d'archéologie chrétienne* (Lyon, Vienne, Grenoble, Genève, Aoste, 21-28 septembre 1986), 1879-1882. Rome 1989.
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↳ Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1907

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– Official or descriptive name: Deir el-Bala'izah

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Other [specify]: Rocky hill used as a rock-cut quarry.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

– Other [specify]: Quarry

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Notes: It is situated in the desert, yet not too far from the Nile valley.

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

A single structure

– No

One single feature

– Other [specify]: No single feature, but features as parts of structures.

A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Notes: It is considered that "some ancient quarries were first fitted out as dwellings; then down the slope, a whole series of buildings was constructed" (Coquin et al. 1991, 786). According to this view, the settlement was developed progressively.

↳ A group of features:

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↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

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↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

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↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Collapsed

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

– Other [specify]: No

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

– Natural phenomena

Notes: Abandoned and deteriorated due to natural decay.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Field doesn't know

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Abba Apollo (Christian Saint).

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Field doesn't know

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

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– Field doesn't know

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Field doesn't know

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

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Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: A significant corpus of Coptic and Greek manuscripts was found in Deir el-Bala'izah (Kahle, P. E. Bala'izah. Coptic Texts from Deir el-Bala'izah in Upper Egypt. London 1954).

Design and Material Remains

Is decoration present:

– No

Notes: Most probably not preserved. Fragments of painted plaster and traces of inscriptions of walls of church.

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– No

Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Notes: Quarry

Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– I don't know

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– I don't know

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– I don't know

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– I don't know

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– I don't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– I don't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– Yes

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– No

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– Yes

↳ Grass

– I don't know

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Mudbrick

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Mudbricks

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– No

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Notes: Quarry

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– I don't know

Is monumental architecture present:

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Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

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↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

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↳ Stone

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↳ Is this material sourced locally:

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↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Mudbrick

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Mudbricks

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– No

Notes: Most probably not preserved. Fragments of painted plaster and traces of inscriptions of walls of church.

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– I don't know

Beliefs and Practices

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Are pilgrimages present:

– I don't know

Is divination present:

– No

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

Notes: Holy Communion

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:
– I don't know

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:
– I don't know

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:
–specify: Unknown. According to Grossmann (1993, 202), the monastery of Bala'iza would be inhabited by a great number of monks (up to 1,000); Wipszycka (2009, 160) debated the suggestion of Grossmann and considered it as an exaggeration.

↳ How often do these rituals take place:
–specify: Unknown.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
– Yes

Notes: Orthodoxy from the Egyptian perspective.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ Are they sky deity:

– Yes

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– Yes

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– No

↳ Are they unquestionably good:
– Yes

↳ Are they other:
– Other [specify]: No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:
– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:
– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:
– Yes

↳ In dreams:
– I don't know

↳ In trance possession:
– No

↳ Through divination practices:
– Yes
Notes: Liturgy. Prayer.

↳ Only through religious specialists:
– Yes

↳ Only through monarch:
– No

↳ Other
– Other [specify]: No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:
– I don't know

Notes: It is unknown whether the monastery attracted pilgrims and visitors.

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Yes

By all the community

– Yes

Notes: It is meant community of the monks.

By specific individuals

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– I don't know

Are formal burials present:

– No

Notes: No cemetery discovered in the site.

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Notes: No cemetery discovered in the site.

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ Are they sky deity:

– Yes

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– Yes

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– No

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Are they other:

–Other [specify]: No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– I don't know

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

Notes: Liturgy. Prayer.

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: No

Are previously human spirits present:

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Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

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Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

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Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

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Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– I don't know

Notes: It is unknown whether the monastery attracted pilgrims and visitors.

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

Notes: Holy Communion

Do large-scale rituals take place:

– I don't know

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– I don't know

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: Unknown. According to Grossmann (1993, 202), the monastery of Bala'iza would be inhabited by a great number of monks (up to 1,000); Wipszycka (2009, 160) debated the suggestion of Grossmann and considered it as an exaggeration.

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: Unknown.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Yes

Notes: Orthodoxy from the Egyptian perspective.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Yes

↳ By all the community

– Yes

Notes: It is meant community of the monks.

↳ By specific individuals

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– I don't know

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– I don't know

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– I don't know

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Notes: Legal documents (appointment of superior, repayments of debts, deeds of sale, receipts, tax-receipts, marriage contract, etc.).

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Yes

↳ Present part time

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– I don't know

Notes: Logically the monks were of Egyptian origin but it could be possible that non Egyptians would have joined the congregation.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– No

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– I don't know

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they written at this place:

– I don't know

↳ Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:

– I don't know

↳ Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Are the scriptures part of the building/place:

– I don't know

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– I don't know

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Yes

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Yes

↳ Present part time

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↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

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↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

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Notes: Logically the monks were of Egyptian origin but it could be possible that non Egyptians would have joined the congregation.

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↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

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Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Yes

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:
Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders
– Yes

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– I don't know

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– I don't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– I don't know

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Notes: Legal documents (appointment of superior, repayments of debts, deeds of sale, receipts, tax-receipts, marriage contract, etc.).

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they written at this place:

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Bibliography

General References

Reference: Deir el-Bala'izah, Monastery of Abba Apollo, Kahle, Paul E.. Bala'izah. Coptic Texts from Deir Al-bala'izah in Upper Egypt. Vol. 1. London: Oxford University Press, 1954.

Reference: Deir el-Bala'izah, Monastery of Abba Apollo, Grossman, Peter. "Die Unterkunftsbauten Des Koinobitenklosters 'dair Al-balayza' Im Vergleich Mit Den Eremitagen Der Mönche Von Kellia". edited by Philippe Bridel. Mission suisse d'archéologie copte, 1986.

Reference: Deir el-Bala'izah, Monastery of Abba Apollo, Petrie, W. M. Flinders. Gizeh and Rifeh. London: Quaritch, 1982.

Reference: Deir el-Bala'izah, Monastery of Abba Apollo, Grossmann, Peter. "Ruinen Des Klosters Dair Al-balaiza in Oberägypten". Jahrbuch Für Antike Und Christentum 36 (n.d.).

Reference: Deir el-Bala'izah, Monastery of Abba Apollo, Goehring, James E.. "The Monastery of Apollo at Bala'iza and Its Literary Texts". In Christianity and Monasticism in Middle Egypt: Minya and Asyut, 41-56. Cairo: The American University in Cairo Press, 2015.